

EXPLORING THE IMPLICATIONS OF TEACHER TURNOVERS IN PRIVATE ACADEMIC INSTITUTIONS: A PERSPECTIVE OF SCHOOL HEADS

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Exploring the Implications of Teacher Turnovers in Private Academic Institutions: A Perspective of School Heads

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Abstract

The purpose of this generic qualitative study is to explore and understand the implications of teachers' turnover from the perspective of the school heads in the private academic institutions. Using the purposive sampling strategy, this study had 10 research participants who underwent in-depth interviews (IDI) at both primary and secondary levels in Tagum City, Davao Del Norte. Five of the 10 research participants came from non-sectarian schools, and the other five were from sectarian private institutions. With the use of the thematic analysis, results revealed that the impact of teacher turnovers are the apprehensions on hiring and training of teacher replacement, workloads and transfer of duties, consistency of teaching methods, and system adaptation, social and career impact of teacher's departure, and acquiring financial and economic stability. The research participants also shared their ways of addressing teacher turnovers, which are through fostering open communication, support, and understanding, nurturing professionalism in resignation from work, adherence to contract and renewal protocols, professional development opportunities, increasing teachers' salaries, provision of additional incentives, and decide autonomy among teachers. In addition, they cited insights that they can share with other school heads who experience turnover, which are: to have mentorship and professional growth, support for various pieces of training, cultivate a positive work culture, provision of contracts, and manage turnover with foresight. The findings of this study can be used to understand the impacts of teacher turnover. Thus, these results can be used by school owners, school heads, and government officials to understand teacher turnover and adopt strategies and insights to improve retention policies and programs to alleviate teacher turnover in private academic institutions.

Keywords: *educational management, school heads, thematic analysis, teacher turnovers, teacher retention*

Introduction

The government and private academic institutions play an interdependent role in the Philippine educational system, as acknowledged by the Philippine constitution (Admin-CRU, 2023). The private sector helps the public, and academic institutions cater to the educational needs of Filipino people. However, the mass resignation of teachers in the private sector is visible. Transferring teachers from the private to the public sector leads to a disparity between the private and government sectors that impacts students' enrollment in the former school and ultimately leads to numerous school closures (Rosario, 2020).

In a study conducted in Private Educational Academies in South Korea, 55 foreign language teachers resigned after finishing the signed one-year contract, revealing that an unfavorable environment, administrative style, and ill-mannered students and parents are reasons for leaving (Dos Santos, 2020). Even though enrollment in private schools has increased in South Asia, teacher turnover is still high, exceeding that in government schools because teachers' compensation in public schools is way higher (Beteille et al., 2020). Moreover, a study revealed that turnover resulted in a shortage of effective teachers internationally and in the United States (Geiger & Pivovarova, 2018). In Australia, the number of job vacancies for private school teachers doubled, with the most severe teacher shortages in 2022. In the national survey, two-thirds of the school heads confirmed that they have insufficient teachers, and 55% are Physics teachers, caused by retirement, migration, and having other opportunities in other academic institutions (Caroll, 2022).

In the Philippines, DepEd Secretary Sara Duterte fears that the significant movement of educators from private to public educational institutions may result in the forced closure of private institutions (Pinlac, 2022). In Cebu City, the additional two years in the secondary level contribute to the increase of teacher shortage since competent teachers transfer to government schools (Oberes & Tan, 2022). Some lawmakers were worried about teacher turnover, which could impact education in the country. Nueva Ecija Rep. Ria Vergara cited that numerous private schools have already been shut down in his district, hoping to have a law that benefits the private school teachers just like the government employees (Rosario, 2020).

In Tagum City, in my experience, several teachers from private academic institutions resigned annually, either finishing the contract or breaching the agreement. The schools provide measures to prevent teachers from leaving, such as penalizing teachers amounting to Php.50,000 - Php.100,000 and offering longer service in the contract. However, teachers still leave. The academe meets, hires, and trains novice teachers to fill the positions of the resigned teachers.

Looking into the works of literature, I have found several published researches related to teacher turnovers. Research findings from Texas point to the severe reductions in human capital over time in all schools, and disparities in turnover patterns for schools serving low-income and minority pupils are concerning (Holme et al., 2018). During the education meeting, Cagayan de Oro City Rep. Rufus Rodriguez mentioned a need to conduct a study that will identify ways to help private schools prevent mass migration (Rosario, 2020). Thus, this study will explore the varied implications of teacher turnover from the perspective of the school heads. Except for the fact

that there is a dearth of research on teacher turnover from the viewpoint of school administrators, this study aims to gain a new perspective and a better understanding of the different implications of teacher turnover from the school heads' perspective, aiming to address turnovers to reduce the number of increasing teacher turnover in the private sector.

Therefore, conducting this study is urgent. The result of this study aims to alleviate teachers' resignations. Gaining an understanding of the different implications of teacher turnover from the perspective of the school heads seeks to improve the standpoint of the policymakers on teachers' turnovers, directing them to address turnovers. The result of this study will be disseminated through publication, re-echo sessions, and research forums and conferences if chance permits. There will also be a copy provided in the school library for reference.

Research Questions

1. What are the implications of teacher turnover in private academic institutions as perceived by school heads?
2. How do school heads address the negative implications of teacher turnover in private academic institutions?
3. What insights relative to teachers' turnover can the participants share with other school heads?

Literature Review

Teacher Turnovers: A Phenomenon

Teacher turnover has become a worldwide problem in many educational systems (Elyashiv, 2019). According to data from the Education Bureau, 3,540 teachers at public elementary and secondary schools have quit their jobs before taking retirement, with annual totals previously hovering around 1,300, which is already 28% higher than the full-year total for the year prior and more than quadruple the number for 2020–21 (Ihara, 2023). A study in Louisiana with early childhood teachers explored the turnover rates of varied programs such as childcare, head start, school, toddler, and preschool and concluded that one-third of teachers teaching was no longer teaching in the next school year; that nearly one-half (46%) of the childcare teachers, 34% of the head start teachers, 26% of the school-based teachers, 49% of toddler teachers, and 31% of preschool teachers transferred and that 37% of teachers were out of the record of Louisiana Center. In comparison, 32% were not written on the record (Bassok et al., 2021).

Moreover, the turnover rates were 39%, and 73% of the teaching vacancies in the state were from secondary schools in Tennessee schools (Merod, 2022). In Wisconsin, the number of teachers quitting their jobs is also rising. Almost 116,000 teachers from around 450 school districts and other K–12 organizations left their positions during the last 15 years and found that turnover increased to close to 16 percent in the 2022–23 school year, up from an average of 11.5 percent since 2009. The 2023 rate includes the second-highest levels of teachers leaving Wisconsin public school classrooms and the most significant levels of teachers migrating between districts on record (Hess, 2023).

In the Philippines, DepEd Secretary Sara Duterte fears that the significant movement of educators from private to public educational institutions may result in the forced closure of private institutions (Pinlac, 2022). In Cebu City, the additional two years in the secondary level contribute to the increase of teacher shortage since competent teachers transfer to government schools (Oberes & Tan, 2022). Some lawmakers were worried about teacher turnover, which could impact education in the country. Nueva Ecija Rep. Ria Vergara cited that numerous private schools have already been shut down in his district, hoping to have a law that benefits the private school teachers just like the government employees (Rosario, 2020).

Further, a research report from the Third American School District Panel Survey presented that educators' turnover rate increased during the pandemic. In School Year 2021–2022, teacher turnover increased by 4% over pre-pandemic reaching 10% nationwide. In the 2022–2023 school year, principal turnover also increased, with a nationwide average of 16 percent (16%). In S.Y. 2021–2022, districts experienced the most significant teacher turnover 2021–2022, ranging from 12–14%, whereas the principal turnovers were between 21 and 23% in rural and high-poverty areas. With this situation, the district leaders were hopeful that staffing shortages will be less severe in 2022–2023 than in 2021–2022. However, staffing shortages fell in 2022 for substitute teachers, exceptional education instructors, and bus drivers (Diliberti & Schwartz, 2021).

Underlying Reasons for Teacher Turnovers

The teachers' intention for turnover varies across countries and schools within countries according to the function of the teacher, the school, and country-level factors (Qin, 2020). A study in South Korea examines 55 foreign language teachers who quit their teaching post after their first-year contract expired. According to the findings, each participant had an unpleasant or unfavorable experience in their social and educational environments, poor management practices by school administrators, and rude parents and pupils' practices considered to be their common intention of leaving (Dos Santos, 2020). According to a different survey, teachers' intentions to leave the profession are primarily motivated by variables connected to the school's approach and workload as well as a lack of professional responsibility (Räsänen et al., 2020). Moreover, another study also claimed that teachers who have thought about leaving cite a number of reasons, including an increase in workload, constant stress, and an inadequate amount of support from parents and administrators (Marshall et al., 2022).

In the United States, unsatisfactory school working conditions and culture related to administrative aspects were known to be the

highest cause of teacher turnover (Young, 2018). A study that explored the working conditions of the 28 ethnically varied teachers within the three chartered schools in New York City enumerated three significant reasons for teacher turnover: working, organizational, and sociocultural conditions. Due to the highly organized and hierarchical environment, schools reported having limited autonomy and decision-making top managers at central offices, who set the standards, and numerous people who valued academic staff such as principals, teachers, and staff as inferior groups (White, 2018).

While the study in the Philippines revealed that the personal variables with environmental change having the greatest impact why teacher leave in the institution. Similarly, the institutional factors had a moderate impact on teacher turnover, primarily due to limited training opportunities (Santiago et al., 2022).

Moreover, a study revealed that the unpleasant administrative style of the school environment is the highest factor in why teachers resign (Dos Santos, 2020). The teacher work satisfaction mediates the impact of principal support on teacher turnover intention (Al-Mahdy & Alazmi, 2023). With this, another study was conducted to measure the principal's dispositions to the effect of their practices in working conditions, affecting teachers' turnover. The study revealed that principals have autocratic dispositions, which agreed they felt better served by less experienced teachers willing to follow their agenda. Regarding the managerial dispositions, the participants mentioned they feel responsible for making decisions; there is no need to train the teachers because they already know what to do. The participants also have a narrow focus accountability disposition, which they have high expectations of the teachers. With this, teachers' performances are measured according to the student's test scores. Their teachers' contracts will be terminated if they do not meet their expectations (Bickmore & Dowell, 2018).

On the one hand, a study conducted through a mail survey with 272 kindergarten teachers revealed that stress affects teacher turnovers (Yang et al., 2018). In light of their teaching backgrounds, a study looked at the relationships among Iranian English as a Foreign Language (EFL) instructors' intentions to leave the field, stress at work, psychological wellness, and tenacity. The 325 EFL teachers (138 new and 187 experienced) revealed a substantial correlation between psychological well-being and occupational stress/turnover intentions among beginner and experienced teachers (Nazari & Oghyanous, 2021).

On the other hand, studies mentioned that compensation is a factor in teacher turnover. A study on private school teachers in Indonesia revealed that their compensation significantly affected their turnovers mediated by organizational commitment (Widodo & Aliffudin, 2021). It might be difficult to recruit and keep teachers when pay is low. Teachers who ultimately left their schools earned less money on average, participated in fewer given extracurricular events that coupled their professional development (like coaching learners or supporting teachers), and pursued more job possibilities outside the educational system than teachers who stayed (García & Weiss, 2019).

For all these reasons, Preechawong et al. (2021) claimed that the strongest indicator of teacher turnover is job satisfaction. Thus, this study emphasized the focus on enhancing the policy that deals with the welfare of the teachers, which will reduce stress and strengthen job satisfaction.

The Positive Implications of Teacher Turnover

With various reasons for teacher turnover, several consequences of teachers leaving occur. Some are positive effects, and some are adverse effects. One of the positive implications of teacher turnover is the chance for the school to hire more effective teachers. Considering the interaction quality of teachers, Bassok et al. (2021) concluded in their study that teachers who work in child care and with younger children had greater turnover rates, and those who leave are assessed as having lower interaction quality than those who stay. In a study by Wyckoff & James (2020), 46% of teacher turnovers rated their effectiveness from S.Y. 2012-203 to 2016-2017. These teachers were marked ineffective, minimally effective, or developing. It was discovered that the newly hired teachers rated more effective than those who left.

In addition, teacher turnover is advantageous to children. In the study conducted in the District of Columbia Public Schools, teacher turnover does not affect student performance, generally math proficiency and reading. In grades with turnover, the SD for math achievement increases by 5% on average for students more than ratings in math and reading, are lost when low-performing (ineffective, marginally effective, or emerging) instructors leave the classroom. Student achievement in arithmetic and reading rises respectively (Wyckoff & James, 2020).

The Negative Implications of Teacher Turnover

With the negative impacts of teacher turnover, teacher shortages rank first. Castro et al. (2018) cited that attrition and turnover among school-level teachers significantly impact the need for teachers. Geiger and Pivovarova (2018) revealed that a shortage of effective teachers is one of the consequences of teacher turnover internationally and in the United States.

The shortage of teachers is considerably worse than currently anticipated when measures of teacher quality consider the certification, pertinent training, and teaching experience, with high-poverty schools suffering the most from the lack of credentialed instructors (García & Weiss, 2019). A study in American School District Panel surveyed 300 district and charter network leaders from October to December 2022 to get a national snapshot of the 2021–2022 turnover and staffing shortages in districts at the start of the 2022–2023 school year. By the end of the 2021–2022 school year, teacher turnover had risen by four percentage points over pre-pandemic averages

to reach 10% nationwide (Diliberti & Schwartz, 2023).

Further, the same study presented the increase of turnovers of school principals hitting 16 percent heading into the 2022–2023 academic year, which was highest (between 21 and 23 percent) in rural and high-poverty districts (Diliberti & Schwartz, 2023). This principal turnover leads to difficulty in finding a replacement for an experienced and effective school principal. Also, principal turnover leads to an increase in teacher turnover (Bartanen et al., 2019).

In addition, another consequence of teacher turnover affects student achievements, especially for schools with many black and low-performing students (Castro et al., 2018). When educators quit or fail to replace them in a timely manner, the educational system faces a severe problem, and learning objectives for the students could suffer as a result of this (Aulia & Haerani, 2023). Effective teaching and learning in schools are weakened by the destructive effects of teacher turnover in other countries and the United States (Boateng & Donkor, 2020). A study measuring the significance of student performance on teacher turnover revealed that the effect of turnover by the highest-rated (highly effective) teachers on student achievement in reading declines by 0.13 SD which occurs because relationships with students are vital to the teachers (Wyckoff & James, 2020).

This study shows that negative emotions and instructional behavior link to unhappiness and attrition. Reducing teacher stress, attrition, and the harmful impacts of stress should concentrate on enhancing teacher-student interactions (Harmsen et al., 2018).

Lastly, the financial aspect of the school is another consequence of teacher turnover. Young (2018) mentioned that schools and districts spend the necessary financial resources available to take the places of leaving teachers. Castro et al., (2018) also added that the states and districts added costs from continuously recruiting, hiring, and developing new teachers to fill the void left by teachers' mobility and attrition, which was estimated by a national analysis of teacher shortage to cost \$2.2 billion annually for attrition and approximately \$4.9 billion annually for replacing teachers who transfer schools.

Strategies to Address the Negative Implications of Teacher Turnover

Several authors reveal different strategies to resolve teacher turnovers. However, some authors shared their recommendations and suggestions for resolving this concern.

With a high percentage of teacher shortages in the USA, state policy, school leaders, district leaders, and decision-makers are severely challenged (Castro et al., 2018). To address it, ninety percent of districts implemented one or more policy adjustments to increase teacher ranks in response to shortages, either on their own or with the help of their state (Diliberti & Schwartz, 2023).

Furthermore, Castro et al., (2018) recommended ways that policymakers should look into to increase the retention of teachers. First, there should be a committed state level of financing. To address teacher shortages in every state, efforts to retain teachers and principals will be essential to more readily uphold the enlistment, maintenance, and improvement of instructors. Holme et al., (2018) suggest that policymakers and school administrators should have the target funding to the relatively few schools that experience teacher turnovers. In order to solve the shortage of teachers, particularly in areas with a high need, states have become more reliant on financial programs. The Rural Recruiting Initiative (RRI) was founded in South Carolina to provide funding for projects aimed at attracting and retaining teachers in remote and other underserved school districts that have serious teacher staffing shortages (Tran & Smith, 2021).

Second, having a systematic of handling the data would help retain teachers. The systems include the enrollment of teachers in preparation, indicators of teacher mobility, the reasons teachers leave the profession, and recognizing deficiencies by the branch of knowledge and school, including the perceptions of the qualified teachers for their schools (Castro et al., 2018). A straightforward approach to school-wide discipline can be a part of this. Research participants confessed that an "Unclear approach to student discipline" is a primary reason for leaving (Kamrath et al., 2020). The report of various types of turnover rates in accountability reports helps parents and the public to be more aware of the impact on the school (Holme et al., 2018).

Third, drafting a solid leadership system is also a great strategy. School administrators might look into effective hiring strategies, eliminating stressful working environments, and support for teachers (Castro et al., 2018). A study claims that the participants' main reason for staying is the school administrator's quality of being supportive of letting them express themselves and allowing them to decide on campus situations (Gilliam-Flentge, 2021). Another study in Kuwait investigates the association between principal support and teacher turnover. With 392 teachers' data from public schools examined, the findings demonstrate that teacher work satisfaction considerably mediates the indirect impact of the support of the principal on teacher turnover intention. This study suggests enhancing the leadership styles of the school principal to lower teacher turnover (Al-Mahdy & Alazmi, 2021).

Fourth, the school administrators can also have leadership preparation programs. The programs include training and workshops on human resource management, healthy working conditions, and factors that impact working conditions (Castro et al., 2018). With healthy working conditions, lower teacher turnovers occur (Geiger & Pivovarova, 2018). However, teachers who express more significant discontent with the leadership and working situations in schools that experience high teacher turnover rates (Young, 2018) and teachers who are highly dissatisfied with their jobs are more likely to leave their profession (Edinger & Edinger, 2018).

Fifth is creating sustainable teacher career pathways that allow teachers to grow personally and professionally. School administrators can support teacher leadership and explore new skills (Castro et al., 2018). To determine the relationship between teacher retention

intentions and leader support, a study surveying 1,114 instructors working in 152 supported by public child care centers collected responses. The findings indicate that, in addition to a number of educator, leader, and center characteristics, leader support is positively correlated with observed teacher retention (Doromal & Markowitz, 2023).

Sixth, the grow-your-own program. This program includes teacher exchange which teachers will be working in another place to learn and benchmark their instructions and practices. As the time frame ended, they had to return to their locality to impart what they had learned (Castro et al., 2018).

Lastly, the ongoing professional development and mentoring. School principals can improve working conditions by reducing teachers' stress and burnout (Castro et al., 2018). Regarding mentoring, the principal's dispositions affect their practices in working conditions which significantly affects teachers' turnover. The study mentioned that the participants mentioned that they did not need to train the teachers because they already knew what to do (Bickmore & Dowell, 2018).

In addition to the enumerated strategies to address teacher turnover, teachers' compensation and recognition are also significant. A study showed that the teacher participants responded that a salary increase is needed for them to stay (Kamrath et al., 2020). The alleged financial difficulties faced by teachers are real. The signs that teacher salary is too low and declining are noted (García & Weiss, 2019). A study of 207 honorary teachers at a private school in Indonesia revealed that compensation, either directly or indirectly through organizational commitment, significantly impacts teachers' intention to leave the profession. (Alifuddin & Widodo, 2021). Low-income schools had higher teacher turnover (Geiger & Pivovarov, 2018).

Moreover, the schools can have activities relating to teachers' recognition. Kamrath et al. (2020) believe recognition is even more important than pay. Teachers who tirelessly educate kids under challenging circumstances want recognition for their dedication.

In conclusion, teacher turnover is a phenomenon that occurs not just in a few but in many places worldwide, resulting in an increase in teaching position vacancies and a shortage of exceptional teachers and staff. With the rapid growth of teacher turnover worldwide, various studies and reports revealed the common factors of teachers leaving from one institution to another. One study claimed participants resigned due to rude parents and pupils' practices. Some studies showed that the workload affects teacher turnover. However, multiple studies cited the common grounds for teacher turnover: poor working conditions, poor administrative style, and compensation.

With this, the extent of teacher turnover resulted in both positive and negative consequences. Several studies revealed that teacher turnover advantageously leads to hiring more competent teachers to replace those who left. Surprisingly, one study cited that teacher turnover does not affect students; however, they perform better in school, gaining better test results. However, teacher turnover adversely affects teacher shortages, which affect the schools, the students, and the community, causing the decline of students' achievements and the schools' finances. Thus, there are suggested actions to mediate this phenomenon that can be used to resolve teacher turnovers.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a generic qualitative research design. The qualitative method is defined as making sense of reality, describing and explaining the social world, and creating descriptive theories and models, and the primary way the theoretical basis of social sciences can be built or reexamined (Morse & Field, 1996). The purpose of qualitative research is to analyze what the respondents stated in order for them to clarify why they have expressed it. It focuses on participants' memories of a life event (Austin & Sutton, 2014).

This study explored the school heads' varied experiences regarding teacher turnover. The different implications of teacher turnover, either negative or positive, and the possible strategies to resolve these negative consequences of teacher turnover will be part of the discussion.

Further, this study specifically used generic qualitative inquiry. The generic qualitative inquiry includes investigating people's accounts of their subjective attitudes, opinions, or reflections on their experiences of objects (Percy et al., 2015). This descriptive methodology discovers how people interpret phenomena or situations based on "what will work best" in addressing the research goals (Said Al Hasni et al., 2023).

The school heads may have different perspectives on teacher turnover depending on their opinions, attitudes, and experiences. The strategies used in resolving this teacher turnover will also be varied. However, these viewpoints can help other school heads better understand teacher turnover and the best method for addressing this situation.

Therefore, this study used a generic qualitative design because the researcher investigated the school heads' subjective perspectives on teacher turnover, specifically its impact on the various private academic institutions, both positive and negative, the strategies to address the negative consequences, and the insights they will share with the other school heads in the private academic institution through the in-depth interviews.

Participants

This generic qualitative study had 10 research participants undergoing in-depth interviews (IDI). Kumar et al. (2020) claimed that eight to ten participants are enough to retain the richness of data. Further, these participants are school heads of basic education, both primary and secondary level, in private academic institutions in Tagum City, Davao Del Norte. Of the ten research participants, five came from non-sectarian schools, and the other five were from sectarian private institutions.

Moreover, this study used the purposive sampling strategy. In qualitative research, purposeful sampling is used to find and choose topics with plenty of relevant information on the cases under study. With this, researchers use criteria-based samples the most frequently (Palinkas et al., 2015). Since the ability to explain a particular issue, concept, or occurrence is a criterion for selecting informants (Robinson, 2017), the criteria for selecting research participants in this study are specified.

In order to choose the research participants in this study, the following criteria were used: (a) must be a school administrator (school principal or school head) of a private academic institution of a basic education level Tagum City, Davao Del Norte and (b) must experience 20% of teacher turnover in his/her administration over the total number of the teachers in the institution.

Procedure

In order to attain the desired outcome of this study, the data collection process was as follows: (a) validation of the research instrument and checking of the informed consent form, (b) seeking of permission from REC to conduct the study, (c) seeking of consent of the research participants, (d) interview and (e) transcribing and storing of data.

Firstly, internal and external validators need to validate the research instrument after the proposal defense and intensive scrutiny of this paper through the routing form. After this, the researcher submitted the manuscript, the various forms needed, the validated interview guide, and the drafted Informed Consent Form that was used during the conduct of this study to the Research Ethics Committee of Mary's College, Inc. After the revisions and the approval of REC together with the Dean of the Graduate School, I received the REC clearance allowing her to conduct of the study.

Next, I sent a printed letter, the endorsement letter from the Dean of the graduate school, an Informed consent form, and the Data Privacy notice directly to the office of the school heads of the private academic institutions at both primary and secondary levels to seek approval to conduct an orientation about the researcher's intention to conduct a study. The orientation was helpful for the researcher to confirm if the pre-determined criteria for selection were met and to ask for permission if the school head was willing to participate in the study. However, in the absence of the school heads, the printed documents were usually received by their secretary, and I waited for the update from the secretary. They usually informed me to wait for a call or text. Some informed me of their School Head's schedule so we could talk personally. Since school heads had already read the printed letter, endorsement letter, ICF, and data privacy notice, I received refusals from several school heads because (a) they needed more time to qualify the criteria and (b) they were too busy to accommodate me.

When school heads provided their schedule, I still informed them about the ICF and the data privacy notice. During the orientation, I asked for the approval of the school head to record the audio for documentation, but a modification of the audio will be performed to protect the participant's identity. The content stipulated in the informed consent form and the Data Privacy in the study was iterated to the research participant. If the participant approves participation, the I sought his/her approval of the Informed Consent Form (ICF) by affixing his/her signature to the certificate of consent. The research participant was provided with a copy of the Data Privacy Notice, and another copy of the Data Privacy Notice was signed and returned to the researcher for documentation.

However, there were school heads I approached about my intention to conduct the study. They will inform me to read all the documents first before giving me a response to my request. After returning to his/her set time, she/he agreed to an interview and asked for availability of his/her time and mode of the interview according to his/her convenience. The interview can be either face-to-face or virtual. For the research participants who did the interview online, we used the online platform that she/he is comfortable with. In this study, only one participant chose to have an online interview.

Since almost all the research participants were interviewed face-to-face, I wore my mask whenever I had transactions with them to observe the COVID-19 protocols. During the interview, the researcher was reminded of the measures taken for data privacy since the interview will be documented, such as the need to wear a cap to cover his/her face in online interviews and modification of his/her voice in the audio devices. I also had a paper and pen for her to jot down the critical information during an interview to avoid misconceptions. For the participant to fully elaborate his/her thoughts, I asked probing questions when needed. I revisited questions not adequately addressed to gather additional data.

Lastly, once all the interviews were gathered, I compiled all her files in one folder on her computer and labeled each document with SH 001, SH 002, and others, while the notes I made will also be compiled in one envelope. Once the data were organized, I transcribed all the recorded conversations word by word. Then, the hard copies will be placed in a plastic envelope and put in an organizer with a lock upon storing the data. In contrast, the softcopies were stored on my computer in a coded folder, which prevented other people from accessing them. The data collected will be kept for three (3) years after the research study is finished, after which it will be securely destroyed to prevent unauthorized access, use, or disclosure to the public or any other party, or as required by law. The

softcopies will be deleted from my computer. At the same time, the hardcopy will be torn into small pieces, soaked in water until dissolved into small unreadable bits, and thrown into the garbage. After that, data analysis followed.

Ethical Considerations

This study aims to explore the implications of teacher turnovers according to the perspective of the school heads. To do this study, the following ethical considerations were observed. Thus, this study was submitted to the Research Ethics Committee for review.

Social Value. A study with societal value should address an essential issue for the community (EUPATI Open Classroom, 2023). This proposed study is seen by the researcher as urgent to be conducted for it has a relevant social value. The conduct of this study will be helpful for private academic institutions, which will benefit the people in the community. Reducing teacher turnover will mainly help teachers, parents, and students. This study benefits the teachers, especially in the private sector, where they will be given a decent and reasonable salary or compensation for the job and responsibility given to them, as well as the students and parents who ensure expert teachers handle their children's education. With this study, private academic institutions aim to develop strategies to reduce teacher turnover, which has a considerable role in employment and education.

Informed Consent. All participants who will participate in every research should be provided with sufficient information about the study to make an informed decision to participate (Siegle, 2023). The researcher submitted a drafted informed consent form to the Research Ethics Committee of SMCTI, Inc. to ensure its validity, appropriateness, and accuracy. After its approval, the informed consent form was given to the research participants with the letter and a data privacy form directly to the school head of the private academic institution office to ask permission to conduct the study. If the school heads met the criteria for selection and approval was granted, the researcher still informed the research participant about the informed consent form and the data privacy notice and had them signed by the research participants.

Vulnerability of Research Participants. The research participants deemed vulnerable are not always vulnerable; their susceptibility could shift depending on their circumstances and surroundings (Research with Vulnerable Groups and Sensitive Topics - School of Social Work and Social Policy - Trinity College Dublin, 2010). During the interview, the researcher does not guarantee that the research participants might not be affected even if they are already professional adults. Their vulnerability depends on their emotional effect on the research questions or topics. However, the researcher guarantees that the discussion was free from offensive statements. Moreover, they can withdraw from the interview if the research participants do not feel like proceeding. Thus, the research participants determined whether to participate in the study.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety. This principle contains two aspects: the research participants should be free from discomfort and harm, and the research participants should be protected from exploitation (Barrow et al., 2022). If the research participants agree to participate in the study, they decide their preferred way of meeting, whether online or face-to-face. Either way, the research participants may face health-related risks and unintended data leak/data breach risks. During a face-to-face meeting, health-related risks, such as COVID-19 and data leak/break, may occur with unforeseen dangers, such as computer technicalities. However, the protocols were strictly followed in the conduct of face-to-face interviews. At the same time, the data gathered from the research participants were stored in a coded folder and organized and locked cabinet. Moreover, participating in this study does not directly benefit the participant, but it contributed to the attainment of the goal of this study, which will help the community.

Privacy and Confidentiality. Privacy is defined as the research participants' ability to manage their personal information, while confidentiality is the researcher's responsibility to safeguard the unauthorized disclosure of information (ATLAS.ti, 2023). To ensure privacy and confidentiality, the researcher shall adhere to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, in which the personal data of research participants will not be reflected in the manuscript except when needed. During the interview, those research participants who wish to conduct the interview online can wear a cap that will not reveal their identity in the video, otherwise, if they permit it. However, in this study, the research participant mentioned that he preferred recording it audio but had to turn his camera off. For those participants who wished to do the face-to-face interview, the researcher modified the audio to prevent the reflection of the participant's identity.

After all the interviews were gathered, the researcher compiled all the files in one folder on the computer and in Google Drive, customized its privacy to the REC for verification, and labeled each document with SH 001, SH 002, and others while the notes will also be compiled in one envelope. The data collected will be kept for three (3) years after the research study is finished, after which it will be securely destroyed to prevent unauthorized access, use, or disclosure to the public or any other party, or as required by law. The softcopies will be deleted from my computer. At the same time, the hard copy will be torn into small pieces, soaked in water until dissolved into small unreadable bits and thrown into the garbage. Moreover, participants who wanted to skip some questions were free to do so during the interview.

Justice. This principle focuses on the researcher's responsibility to treat participants reasonably and equitably (Maheux-Pelletier et al., 2016). To ensure the fairness of this study, the researcher provides the validity of this research and the research instrument. This study underwent defense and keen scrutiny by the panelists and the members of the Research Ethics Committee, while the research instrument underwent validation by varied research experts. In addition, the research participants were identified according to the criteria for selection, including the excluding criteria. The researcher ensured that there would be fair treatment among all research participants. Moreover, all participating school heads of this study received compensation for their time participating.

Transparency. When a study is transparent, everyone can see the process and results of the completed research (Research Health Authority, 2023). To ensure the clarity of this study, the researcher informed the research participants of all the information in the study through the informed consent form. The researcher provided a copy of the informed consent form with the letter and data privacy notice to the offices of the research participants and discussed the content of the Informed Consent Form during the orientation, including the data privacy notice. Then, the participants decided whether to grant permission to continue the interview. If the request is given and the interview is successful, the analyzed data are returned to the participant through member checking. If there is no problem, the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered will reflect on the results, recommendations, and conclusions.

Qualification of the Researcher. Qualified Researchers are needed in the ethical conduct of research. Through their prior experiences, they will be able to meet the criteria for approval (Ethicist, 2016). The researcher is currently taking her master's degree and is qualified to conduct this study based on her knowledge and training. However, there are unclear and misunderstood steps in the study that the researcher needs clarification which is why her research adviser, the more knowledgeable others, will guide her.

Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher is responsible for knowing the resources needed to conduct the study (Research University of Washington, 2023). The researcher will ensure the completeness of the needed facilities. She can access local libraries and the internet and owns gadgets. The school and community have a local library open to anyone, including the researcher, to gather data needed to support this study. The campus and the researcher's mobile devices have internet access for a more comprehensive data source. Further, mobile devices and laptops are also available for online or face-to-face interviews to record the discussion.

Community Involvement. Community involvement guarantees that conducting the study and its output is important and sensitive to humanity (Tamariz et al., 2015). The community will be involved with this study in two ways – the data-gathering process and the benefits of this study. During the data-gathering process, this study required the help of the school heads who participated as research participants. Moreover, the result of this study will benefit people in the community, such as teachers, students, and parents, since teacher turnover affects education and employment. Furthermore, this study can also be used for future researchers in the community for future reference.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings of the data collected. It shows the implications of teacher turnover, strategies to address it, and the insights relevant to it—the significant themes formed to address the research questions and deliberately elaborate the answers to each research question.

Implications of Teacher Turnover in Private Academic Institutions as Perceived by School Heads

After analyzing the data from the research participants, the following are the various effects or consequences of teacher turnover in private academic institutions as perceived by school heads: (a) apprehensions on hiring and training of teacher replacement, (b) workloads and transfer of duties, (c) consistency of teaching methods, and system adaptation, (d) social and career impact of teacher's departure, (e) acquiring financial and economic stability.

Table 1 shows the major themes and core ideas about the implications of teacher turnover in private academic institutions as perceived by school heads.

Table 1. Major Themes and Core Ideas on the Implications of Teacher Turnover in Private Academic Institutions as Perceived by School Heads

Major Themes	Core ideas
Apprehensions on Hiring and Training of Teacher Replacement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • having trouble finding a suitable replacement teacher • managing the various hiring processes • concerns with hiring a replacement teacher due to the short notice of departing • spending more time and effort on training new teachers • customizing training to fit to the new teaching role • harmonizing the retention policies with the new teaching role • additional workload to train new teachers • serving as a substitute for the teacher during the period when they abruptly left
Work Loads and Transfer of Duties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • expressing concerns about the modification in duties and tasks • having difficulty in the alignment of culture to the new school environment
Consistency of Teaching Methods, and System Adaptation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • adjusting to the replacement teacher's methods of teaching • variation in the ways that teachers teach
Social and Career Impact of Teacher's Departure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • expressing emotional attachment when the teacher has left • being able to establish a teacher-pupil relationship

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • acknowledging the improvements, the new teacher will bring • priority to be hired in a higher-ranking teaching position • stepping stone toward career advancement • having a retirement annuity
Acquiring Financial and Economic Stability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • having the opportunity for expense reduction for the institution when hiring new teachers. • having obligation for a salary increase

Addressing the Negative Implications of Teacher Turnover in Private Academic Institutions

In this part, research participants shared strategies for addressing the challenges they faced with teacher turnovers in their institutions. This study arrived at the following themes: (a) fostering open communication, support, and understanding, (b) nurturing professionalism in resignation from work, (c) adherence to contract and renewal protocols, (d) professional development opportunities, (e) increasing teachers’ salaries, (f) provision of additional incentives, and (g) decide autonomy among teachers.

Table 2 below shows how school heads address the negative implications of teacher turnover in private academic institutions.

Table 2. *Major Themes and Cores Ideas about Addressing the Negative Implications of Teacher Turnover in Private Academic Institutions*

Major Themes	Core ideas
Fostering Open Communication, Support, and Understanding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • seeking proper communication channels • having wider considerations of teacher’s concerns • fostering regular communication in addressing needs and concerns
Nurturing Professionalism in Resignation from Work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • encouraging graceful exits • urging fulfillment of contractual obligations • ensuring completion of necessary tasks before leaving
Adherence to Contract and Renewal Protocols	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ensuring compliance with contractual agreements • honoring the significance of contracts as teachers • adhering to stipulated terms and renewal processes
Professional Development Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • offering master’s programs for tenured teachers • offering scholarships for professional development opportunities
Increasing Teachers’ Salaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • providing training to newly hired teachers • providing competitive salary packages to tenured teachers • increasing teacher’s salary level to the public school • discussing teacher’s salaries with the compensation committee • improving the teacher’s basic salary • giving monetary incentives to tenured teachers • providing allowance, and government benefits on top of the basic salary
Provision of Additional Incentives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • granting teachers with free housing incentive • receiving Parents’ School Association subsidy
Decide Autonomy among Teachers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • accepting that school heads cannot compel from teachers leaving • lacking administrative initiatives to encourage teacher retention • emphasizing teachers’ freedom to leave for personal growth

Insights of School Heads on Teacher Turnover that Can Be Shared with Others

The school heads of the private academic institutions shared various points relative to teacher turnover with the other school heads who also experienced teacher turnover. The following are the central themes extracted from the responses of the research participants: (a) provide mentorship, (b) support trainings and professional growth, (c) cultivating positive work culture, (d) provision of contracts, and (e) manage turnover with foresight.

Table 3 shows the major themes and core ideas about the insights of the research participants that they can share with the other school heads who also experience teacher turnovers.

Table 3. *Major Themes and Core Ideas on the Insights of School Heads on Teacher Turnover that Can Be Shared with Others*

<i>Major Themes</i>	<i>Core ideas</i>
Support Trainings and Professional Growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> allow teachers to attend government-provided trainings send teachers to school-funded expense training train teachers about classroom management and assessment strategies have a consistent in-house training utilize one-year contracts
Provision of Contracts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> have renewal agreement of contracts based on the performance of the parties implement contracts to mitigate turnover effects have a two-year contract have strategic plans for teacher turnover acknowledge teacher turnover
Manage Turnover with Foresight	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> be proactive in managing turnover contemplate teacher retention
Provide Mentorship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> mentor the neophyte teachers maximize teachers' capacity to become effective employees guide teachers for holistic development foster leadership style for harmonious relations with teachers
Cultivating Positive Work Culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> create a supportive working environment for teachers building friendship and teamwork in the workplace

Implications of Teacher Turnover in Private Academic Institutions as Perceived by School Head

When teachers leave an institution, they carry reasons for leaving—the reasons may be due to better opportunities outside the institution or disagreements within the institution itself. However, whatever reason it may be, when teachers leave, the school community is affected.

In this study, after analyzing the data from the research participants, the following are the various effects or consequences of teacher turnover in private academic institutions as perceived by school heads: (a) apprehensions on hiring and training of teacher replacement, (b) workloads and transfer of duties, (c) consistency of teaching methods, and system adaptation, (d) social and career impact of teacher's departure, (e) acquiring financial and economic stability.

Apprehensions on Hiring and Training of Teacher Replacement

One of the primary effects of teachers leaving the institution is the challenge of looking for replacements for outgoing teachers and training for newly hired teachers. School heads need help in teacher recruitment to replace the teacher who would leave the institution, especially when teachers suddenly leave the institutions, which leads to trouble.

Experiencing teacher turnover must be traumatic for school heads since the burden of looking after the class is their primary responsibility. So, when teachers leave, the school is left with an empty position, wondering where to find teachers who will replace the outgoing ones. However, if the institution can find replacement teachers, school heads face challenges in training new teachers and have difficulty in adapting to the new environment.

Attrition and turnover among school-level teachers significantly impact the need for teachers (Castro et al., 2018). The concern about the difficulty of hiring new teachers to replace outgoing teachers connects to the challenges of looking for teachers with good qualities to handle the position like outgoing teachers. It refers to the shortage of qualified teachers (García & Weiss, 2019).

With this, impart in the classroom, newly hired teachers should have the skills and knowledge needed to be sufficiently gained from the pre-service training. The minimum qualification for teachers in the Philippines to be eligible to teach in private or public schools is to earn a four-year degree diploma and have a license as a professional teacher (UNICEF, 2019).

So, with newly hired teachers, they should be trained which is costly. The school districts could invest in new student programs or technology if fewer teachers were replaced instead of funding recruitment and training. Higher retention of educators indicates less financial strain and more significant investment in the resources children require to learn (American University, 2023).

Sadly, the shortage of teachers is considerably worse than currently anticipated when measures of teacher quality consider the certification, pertinent training, and teaching experience, with high-poverty schools suffering the most from the lack of credentialed instructors (García & Weiss, 2019).

Workloads and Transfer of Duties

Another implication when teachers leave the institution is workloads and transfer of duties. When teachers leave, the school will be affected especially when handling the tasks and responsibilities of the teacher who left. School heads get an additional workload to train new teachers and teachers who are staying assume the role of substitute teacher during the period especially if the turnover happens abruptly. Unfortunately, the modification in duties and tasks usually results in misunderstanding and ineffective outcomes.

Ardila (2023) introduced cross-training in an organization which is to improve each employee's skill set so they can all comprehend what it requires to keep the business operating. As a result, organizations are better equipped to find internal support work when things get busy or a key employee leaves or is unavailable. Workers acquire knowledge and skills that advance their careers and make them more valuable assets to the organization. However, the additional workload without additional compensation is considered the disadvantage of cross-training. Also, Junaidi et al. (2020) revealed that reasons for employees to leave the job were highly impacted by overtime, job stress, and workload.

Consistency of Teaching Methods, and System Adaptation

Teachers' teaching methods, techniques, and methods are unique. Teachers' behavior, attitudes, and systems differ from one another. So, when the teacher leaves an academic institution, students will be exposed to new teaching styles and systems. Negatively, students experience inconsistent teaching styles because of the styles of their teachers leaving. Then, new teachers come in so that they will adjust along with the teacher's behavior. Students are confused about the various teaching styles and systems implemented since the newly hired teachers are still adapting to the responsibilities and tasks. In contrast, the favorable implication for the students with teacher turnover may introduce better changes in the institution. Students will be able to try better teaching styles and systems.

With this, the researchers discovered students get low achievement because of teacher turnover due to swapping teachers with less effective than those who left the poor performance of newly hired teachers, and organizational disruptions (Donley et al., 2019). However, considering the interaction quality of teachers, Bassok et al. (2021) concluded that teachers who work in child care and with younger children had excellent turnover rates, and those who leave are assessed as having lower interaction quality than those who stay. In a study by Wyckoff & James (2020), forty-six of teacher turnovers rated their effectiveness from S.Y. 2012-203 to 2016-2017. It was discovered that the newly hired teachers rated more effective than those who left.

Social and Career Impact of Teacher's Departure

Another implication when teachers leave the institution is the social and career impact. When teachers leave, the people within the school community are affected, especially students, parents, and teachers. Students and parents are affected emotionally as there is a need to adjust every time new teachers are hired. However, for the teachers who left the institution, teacher turnovers benefited teacher's careers. The private academic institutions are considered training grounds for newly graduated licensed teachers. Since the teachers had already gained experience, teachers who had left top-ranked in the application results were more likely to get hired.

The quality of the relationship between teachers and pupils strongly connects with school liking, peer acceptance, academic performance, self-concept, and emotional control in children (Garcia-Rodriguez et al., 2023). So, when a teacher decides to leave the classroom, it can have various consequences for their students' learning, emotions, and academic performance. They may feel anxious, distressed, insecure, or lose trust. Losing the relationship can cause experiences of being left behind and confusion, resulting in feelings of stress, anxiety, and uncertainty (Satchel Pulse, 2023).

Moreover, the emotional burden of the students is also academically affected. Castro et al. (2018), student achievements are affected due to teacher turnover, especially in schools with many black and low-performing students. Boateng and Donkor (2020) added that effective teaching and learning in schools are weakened by the destructive effects of teacher turnover in other countries and the United States.

Further, children and parents frequently experience feelings of loss after bonding with the teacher. Also, because parents value their children's close relationships with the teachers, they are naturally worried about how their children will react if the teacher leaves (Bright Horizon, 2024).

However, a study said that educators left the school to gain experience. They make private educational institutions into training grounds (Aduna et al., 2020). Aspiring and present educators may require teaching expertise to qualify for a desirable position, advance their careers, or learn from educational professionals. Experience in teaching broadens knowledge, improves skills, and creates networks. Opportunities can be found through both traditional and non-traditional channels (Editorial Team, 2022).

Acquiring Financial and Economic Stability

One of the difficulties private academic institutions face is managing their resources. The school handles all of the operations in the school, from the buildings and facilities to the compensation of teachers and staff, and so on. So, when teachers leave a private academic institution, it benefits the school in terms of compensation. Instead of increasing the salary of tenured teachers, it will go back to the basic pay of the entry-level, and there is no need for an obligatory increase and pay for the retirement annuity.

Labuguen (2022) clarified that the position in the public school determines the public teacher's salary, while in private schools, the school administration determines teachers' salaries based on the school's budget. The fund is heavily influenced by the number of students enrolled in a given school year. Public school teachers earn seventy-two percent more on average than private school teachers. The disparity is even more pronounced in private schools. There is no denying that some private schools cannot adequately compensate their teachers. They receive only enough to keep a few meals on their plates and insufficient to cover their monthly expenses

Although teacher turnover is costly in terms of the hiring process and training for newly hired teachers. Young (2018) mentioned that schools have to recruit and teach each replacement teacher, which consumes valuable time, personnel, and monetary resources. Castro et al. (2018) added that the states and districts added costs from continuously recruiting, hiring, and developing new teachers to fill the void left by teachers' mobility and attrition, which was estimated by a national analysis of teacher shortage to cost two and two billion dollars annually for attrition and approximately four and nine billion dollars annually for replacing teachers who transfer schools; however, compensation-wise and retirement-wise, the school will be able to save cost. Teacher turnover also costs the school money.

Addressing the Negative Implications of Teacher Turnover in Private Academic Institutions

The search participants shared strategies for addressing the challenges they faced with teacher turnovers in their institutions. This study arrived at the following themes: (a) fostering open communication, support, and understanding, (b) nurturing professionalism in resignation from work, (c) adherence to contract and renewal protocols, (d) professional development opportunities, (e) increasing teachers' salaries, (f) provision of additional incentives, and (g) decide autonomy among teachers.

Fostering Open Communication, Support, and Understanding

One of the strategies for addressing teacher turnover is effective communication. School heads are at the forefront of efforts to decrease this high turnover. So, fostering open communication with teachers, advising teachers to seek proper communication channels, having wider consideration of teacher's concerns, and fostering regular communication in addressing needs and concerns were implemented. One of its activities is to have an open forum so the concerns of the teachers can be addressed. Moreover, when the school heads receive feedback about the teachers' performance, the school heads may weigh things first before reacting. Listen to the teacher's point of view first.

Through improving communication, the school fosters an environment that promotes teacher retention (Jotform, 2023). In a particular study in Arizona, the researcher discovered that schools with more satisfied teachers had lower attrition rates and schools with a higher proportion of economically disadvantaged and minority students. These findings support the hypothesis that working conditions mediate the relationship between school demographic information and teacher attrition (Geiger & Pivovarova, 2018).

Further, the essence of feedback, listening to their concerns, and taking action on the teachers' concerns is relevant to fostering open communication in the workplace. When school heads listen to teachers' opinions, they may create an open and accepting workplace that allows teachers to adapt during stressful situations (Rave et al., 2022). So when faced with complaints, school heads must be clear when expressing their intentions when intervening in a parent-teacher conflict to avoid misunderstandings among all parties involved (Samuels, 2019).

Nurturing Professionalism in Resignation from Work

School heads cannot stop teachers from leaving the institution. So, a policy of proper turnover can be practiced. First, encouraging teachers to have graceful exits which means submitting necessary documents and complying with the clearance before leaving. Teachers who plan to resign must inform the administration ahead of time and have the clearance before leaving. Second, advocating for full academic year service before turnover. Teachers must finish the contract or the entire school year and practice a culture of proper turnover to avoid staffing disruptions.

As Özdemir et al., (2021) mention, teacher turnover occurs at the teacher's freedom of choice but Peetz (2023) cited, mid-year teacher resignations are particularly difficult for districts. They exacerbate already challenging staffing shortages, necessitate long-term replacements or other stopgap policies, and undermine principals' educational objectives for the year. With proper turnover, Ekpezu (2023) said that the teachers will be more professional, and there will be a smooth transition from one teacher to another.

Adherence to Contract and Renewal Obligations

To mitigate the fast turnover of teachers in private academic institutions, a system of contract and renewal protocols can be imposed. The teachers qualified for a teaching position sign a contract or agreement to render a service within a time frame set by the school. With contracts, there a stipulated terms and renewal processes and policies that facilitate strategic transitions.

Employment contracts, also known as instructing contracts, are vital records. They are essential to comprehending teachers' rights, responsibilities, and working conditions. The employment contract includes essential details such as the job length, the teacher's responsibilities, expected compensation, the reason for termination, and other terms and conditions. Regarding employment duration, once the period is up, the parties can enter into a new contract or actively agree to a continuing one (Yeban, 2023).

In addition, Yeban (2023) further explained that either party can breach teacher employment contracts. Administrators at the school

may breach the contract, the board of directors, or the teacher. Monetary damages are the most common solution for violating a contract between an educational institution and a teacher.

Professional Development Opportunities

Another strategy to address the implications of teacher turnover is professional development opportunities. School heads can offer scholarships for professional development opportunities. Teachers can enroll in to master's degree program which will be funded by the school. In return, additional years depending on their agreed years of service can be rendered. More so, schools also may provide training to newly hired teachers to improve their skills and knowledge in teaching. Trainings can support teacher's growth and retention because these programs help create a positive work environment.

In connection, creating a sustainable teacher career pathway that allows teachers to grow personally and professionally is one way of mitigating teacher turnover (Castro et al., 2018). A study by Doromal and Markowitz (2023) indicates that leader support is positively correlated with observed teacher retention in addition to several educators, leader, and center characteristics. Thus, Llego (2020) said that master's degrees provide teachers with a more developed, relevant understanding of their chosen subject and may enhance an educator's teaching abilities.

Increasing Teachers' Salaries

Since there is a huge difference in the remuneration between public and private school teachers, the school heads may provide competitive salary packages to tenured teachers. A policy to give increments in teachers' wages every time the additional year is rendered can be applied. Additionally, the increase in teachers' salary level or even the entry level the same as the public school can also be considered.

Even DepEd recognized a significant disparity in teacher salaries between private and public schools. So far, DepEd has declined pay raises for teachers in public schools while promising to look into ways to enhance their non-wage benefits. It fears that raising their salaries will encourage teachers from private institutions to transfer to public educational institutions, which could contribute to the closing of many private schools (Tadle, 2022).

In addition, a study of 207 honorary teachers at a private school in Indonesia revealed that compensation, either directly or indirectly through organizational commitment, significantly impacts teachers' intention to leave the profession (Alifuddin & Widodo, 2021). A study showed that the teacher participants responded that a salary increase is needed for them to stay (Kamrath et al., 2020).

Moreover, Geiger & Pivovarova (2018) revealed that low-income schools had higher teacher turnover and García & Weiss (2019) cited that the alleged financial difficulties faced by teachers are real. The signs that teacher salaries are too low and declining.

Provision of Additional Incentive

On top of the salary, school heads can also provide additional incentives to address teacher turnovers. The incentives can be both monetary and nonmonetary provided by the school and the parents. Teachers may have the Cost of Living Allowance (COLA), government benefits, loyalty awards intended for teachers who stay longer in the institution, and Parents' School Association subsidy for monetary incentives. For the nonmonetary incentives, free housing incentives and teamwork activities for teachers can also be provided.

With this, an incentive is an object item or a desired behavior or occurrence provided by employers to motivate employees to do more work. Incentives are of two types: monetary or financial incentives and nonmonetary incentives (PeopleHum, 2023).

Moreover, Cherry (2023) agrees that when teachers are provided with incentives to stay longer, they will not leave the school because they are motivated to embody that rule to get the rewards known as incentives when teachers are provided with incentives to stay longer, they will not leave the school because they are motivated to embody that rule to get the rewards known as incentives.

Decide Autonomy among Teachers

The school heads cannot compel teachers from leaving, so to address teacher turnover is to allow autonomy among teachers. It means that school heads accept that teachers leave the institution as it is the teachers' freedom to leave for personal growth. With this, schools do not have administrative initiatives to encourage teacher retention. The school keeps on hiring teachers. When the teacher leaves, another teacher gets hired. It allows the teachers to leave the institution and be supported with the future endeavor.

Some authors mentioned the need to have policy adjustments to address teacher turnovers. To address teacher turnovers, Diliberti & Schwartz (2023) said that districts implemented one or more policy adjustments to increase teacher ranks in response to shortages, either on their own or with the help of their state. Unfortunately, some schools do not have a policy or teacher retention policy to address teacher turnover. However, Özdemir et al. (2021) emphasized that teacher turnover happens because it's the choice of the teachers to leave.

Insights of School Heads on Teacher Turnover that can be Shared with Others

The research participants shared various points relative to teacher turnover which they can share with the other school heads who also

experienced teacher turnover. The following are the main themes extracted from the responses of the research participants: (a) provide mentorship, (b) support for various trainings and professional growth, (c) cultivating positive work culture, (d) provision of contracts, and (d) manage turnover with foresight.

Provide Mentorship

School heads may provide mentorship among teachers especially to the neophyte teachers through maximizing teachers' capacity to become effective employees and guiding teachers for holistic development. Although teachers leave one day, school heads can still maximize the teachers to their fullest potential while staying in the institution. In addition, heads may not just focus on one aspect of the teacher or just developing the teacher's academic areas but also the other areas like the spiritual area which means the holistic development among teachers.

Jato and Okemasisi (2022) found that mentorship roles significantly impact the academic achievement of recently deployed/transferred teachers. Bickmore & Dowell (2018) also added that regarding mentoring, the principal's dispositions affect their working practices, significantly affecting teachers' turnover.

In addition, mentorship and looking into the teachers' improvements is the school heads' mere responsibility. The head of the school makes sure their management is supportive, with a focus on the professional growth of their employees (The Alberta Teachers' Association, 2023).

Support to Various Trainings and Professional Growth

School heads must manage turnover while ensuring teachers are well-supported in attending various trainings and professional growth-related activities. Allowing teachers to attend government-provided training, shoulder the training's fee for teachers, and even conduct regular in-house training is beneficial for teacher's growth. In most cases, schools would fund the expenses of the training, however, some are paid by the teachers, especially the trainings provided by the government agencies such as the Private Education Assistance Committee (PEAC) and the Department of Education.

In line with this, Castro et al., (2018) mentioned that one of the strategies to address teacher turnover is ongoing professional development and mentoring. Bawinile Lamula-Mthanti & Msiza (2023) supported that although school heads do not have an active role in developing teachers, their social and financial support helps teachers grow professionally. However, The Alberta Teachers' Association (2023) highlighted that the school head should support teachers through their initial period of employment and understand the developmental stages of preservice and in-service teachers

Cultivating a Positive Work Culture

School heads must manage turnover by cultivating a positive work culture by fostering a leadership style for harmonious relations with teachers and creating a supportive working environment for teachers. The leadership style can be not too strict, not too lenient, or both not too strict and lenient. Further, to create a supportive working environment is to have an open forum and team working activities to understand teachers and take action with their concerns.

Accordingly, with healthy working conditions, lower teacher turnovers occur (Geiger & Pivovarova, 2018). However, teachers who express more significant discontent with the leadership and working situations in schools that experience high teacher turnover rates (Young, 2018) and teachers who are highly dissatisfied with their jobs are more likely to leave their profession (Edinger & Edinger, 2018).

With this, McDonald (2021) shared it is important to note that the management style of the school heads makes a relevant impact on the school because it sets the tone for the whole school community

Provision of Contracts

School heads must manage turnover with contracts. Contracts are agreements that can mitigate turnover effects like leaving the school in the middle of the school year. School heads can utilize one-year contracts or two-year contracts and have a renewal agreement of contracts based on the performance of the parties. The school cannot force teachers to stay at the same time, the school cannot renew the teacher with poor performance within the school year. Usually, if the teacher breaches the contract, the school penalizes the teacher according to the agreement in the contract.

This contracting system allows the schools to hire effective or better teachers for the next school year. It is accordingly, one of the positive implications of teacher turnover is the chance for the school to hire more effective teachers (Bassok et al., 2021). Yeban (2023) said that these contracts that end for a specific duration are known as nonrenewal contracts. If it expires, both parties must decide to sign another employment contract for continuing service or employment. In addition, if one party breaches the contract, the usual solution is to resolve this with monetary damages.

Manage Turnover with Foresight

School heads must manage turnover with proactive measures ahead of time. It means that school heads should accept teacher turnover

as a phenomenon that is still occurring, and one of the most challenging realities in the private sector due to various reasons, as the public school has better salaries than private school, having better opportunities outside, and so on. So, the strategic plan for teacher turnover is to be proactive in managing turnover and contemplating teacher retention. It means that school heads should have a strategic preparedness plan if turnover happens.

Accordingly, these are called proactive measures which are defined as preventive measures taken to prevent incidents from happening. These measures are called strategies to mitigate the damage from the incident in the workplace (Byrd & Henrichson, 2024). It is part of a solid leadership system that school administrators might look into effective hiring strategies to address teacher turnovers (Castro et al., 2018).

Implications for Administrative Practice

The result of this study deals with the experiences of the school heads of private academic institutions regarding the impact of teacher turnover on the students, parents, teachers, and the institution, as well as the strategies used by the school heads to address teacher turnovers and their insights of teacher turnovers that they can share with the other school heads. The following implications for administrative practice have been made with the research findings.

First, school heads should have a clear hiring and replacement policy. Research findings cited that school heads who experienced teacher turnovers stated that they cannot compel teachers from leaving since they have a choice in their career path. With this, school heads must improve the policy of the hiring process which involves clear stipulation of contracts with a specific time frame. If teachers leave or breach that contract, school heads should have strategic plans to replace the outgoing teachers with competent and qualified teachers in order not to disrupt the operation of the institution.

As such, school heads should also focus on the retention policy of the teachers. The research findings suggested fostering effective communication within the workplace, having justifiable remuneration, having additional incentives, providing mentorship, and supporting training and professional growth to teachers. Exposing teachers to these strategies can result in a supportive and positive work culture that can help teachers stay longer in the institution.

Moreover, school heads should manage teacher turnover with a foresight strategy. Research findings cited that school heads should acknowledge that teacher turnover occurs and have strategic plans for teacher turnover. It is also important to be proactive in managing turnover which means to impose the culture of proper exit because even with a contract, teachers still leave. This includes involving departing teachers in transitional planning, submitting necessary documents complying with the clearance before leaving, and advocating for full academic year service before turnover.

Conclusions

Teachers are vital in every academic institution. The absence and leaving of every teacher in the academe affects various individuals in the school community, which includes the students, the teachers, school heads, and even the state of the school. Different research findings claimed that several factors influence teachers' leaving, such as an unhealthy environment, the amount of compensation, and the like.

This study revealed that school heads are aware of the factors that cause teachers to leave and experience the extreme impact after the teachers leave. Various strategies were also implemented to at least reduce the number of turnovers, which can be emulated and enhanced by the other school heads who also experienced teacher turnover.

Therefore, schools cannot force teachers to do not resign, but if schools can provide good reasons to stay, teachers may find the academe worthy of dwelling.

It has been observed that the purpose of this study has been achieved. It explored the different implications of teacher turnover from the perspective of the school heads in private academic institutions, learned strategies to address the negative consequences of teacher turnover, and explored insights relating to teacher turnover. Also, it has been observed that the necessary themes were derived to answer the research questions of this study.

However, it is noted that in this study, only in-depth interviews (IDI) were used as a data-gathering technique, and it is recognized that one of its drawbacks is the need for more data triangulation. Moreover, due to the limited number of research participants and the absence of data triangulation, this study is less generalizable, meaning that the implications of teacher turnovers from the school heads' perspective can only be valid to the research participants.

With this, it is recommended that other researchers copy this research topic in their specific places, in more extensive research participants, or having the same topic but situated in public schools to compare the study results. Researchers may also use methodologies other than in-depth interviews in data gathering. They can also have the same research participants measuring whether they changed their perspective towards teacher turnovers. It is also suggested to explore how private academic institutions properly allocate their finances to school operations.

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